

THE φ -SCALE OF POTENTIAL, AND ITS APPLICATION TO SOME
ELECTROCHEMICAL PROBLEMS. PART II. INVESTIGATION
OF INHIBITION ACTION OF ORGANIC COMPOUNDS

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In the present paper, ϕ -scale of electrode potentials has been utilised in the investigation of mild steel corrosion inhibition in acidic solutions with different types of organic compounds as inhibitors. It was found that ϕ -scale of potentials gave a possibility for the electrocapillary data to be used both for qualitative and quantitative study of inhibitors' action. For example, it proved possible to determine, by means of electrocapillary curves, the alteration of inhibitors' efficiency with the change in their concentration. Several further applications of this method have been discussed. It has been shown also that ϕ -scale of potentials gives a basis for elucidation of the main condition under which any other indirect methods (differential capacity measurements, suppression of polarographic maxima, etc.) can lead to the results comparable with the direct estimation of decrease of corrosion rate due to inhibitors' influence.

In the first paper of this series (Antropov, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 309), a new scale of electrode potential, φ -scale, in which the null-point of metal is chosen as the basis, has been discussed (see also Antropov, *J. Phys. Chem., USSR.*, 1951, 25, 1494; *Proc. Electrochem. Cong.*, 1953, 380, Moscow; *Uspechy Khimii, USSR.*, 1956, 25, 1043 et seq). It has been shown that, when for two different metals, M_1 and M_2 , the values of φ -potentials are equal ($_{M_1}\varphi = _{M_2}\varphi$), their charges and the conditions of physical adsorption on the surface of these metals in contact with solutions are also similar. This provides a possibility of comparing the data obtained for different metals, when the criterion mentioned above is fulfilled. It can also be utilised in the study of corrosion inhibition in acidified solutions, where different types of organic compounds are used as inhibitors. This inhibition action is probably connected with the physical adsorption on metal—solution interface, and therefore depends on the charge of metal with respect to the solution. The most direct evidence, and the quantitative characteristic of adsorption from solutions at different potentials, can be obtained by means of electrocapillary curves. In the present paper this method has been used, and its results have been compared with those of corrosion experiments, taken from literature sources.

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E X P E R I M E N T A L

Electrocapillary curves have been obtained by means of a capillary electrometer (Fig. 1). It differs from the usual

type only by the process of producing the pressure. The necessary pressure can be reached by means of a small rubber bladder, and the excess can be removed by means of a thin glass tube connected with the three-way stop-cock. The capillary can be easily replaced, for there is a ground-glass joint, introduced in this modified form. Potentials are read from a Cambridge portable potentiometer. The values of surface tension (σ) have been calculated from the equation:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{2} g r \rho_{Hg} (h_1 - h_2 + h_m) \dots (1)$$

where r is the radius of the capillary, h_1 , the height of mercury column, h_2 , the height of the position of Hg inside the capillary from capillary tip,

h_m , the difference in heights of mercury in the manometric tube of the electrometer, ρ_{Hg} , the density of mercury and g , the acceleration due to gravity = 978.2 dynes/cm².

Before each experiment, a few droplets of mercury were pumped out to provide a fresh surface of mercury. The surface, thus obtained, was kept in contact with the solution of an organic compound in 1N-H₂SO₄ for nearly $\frac{1}{2}$ hour to reach an equilibrium. All experiments were carried out at room temperature ($25^\circ \pm 2^\circ$) and a 1N-H₂SO₄ solution (Analar) in bidistilled water (to avoid possible contamination by surface active materials) was used. The organic compounds with their respective grades, selected for this electrocapillary experiments, are: thiourea (A. R.), diethylamine (B.D.H.-L.R.), aniline (Nadia Chemical, L.R.), quinoline (B. D. H. - L.R.), β -naphthoquinoline (B.D.H.-L.R.) and pyridine (Analar, distilled).

For all these compounds, the variation of the inhibition action with concentration is given in the literature. For some of them (vide Fig. 9), the electrocapillary curves were obtained previously, and therefore a comparison of our results with those of others was possible.

FIG. 1

(1) Capillary. (2) Ground-glass joint. (3) Platinum wire (sealed), electric connection. (4) Mercury filling tube. (5) Manometric tube. (6) Reservoir for mercury. (7) Three-way cock. (8) Glass capillary for excess pressure removal. (9) Rubber bladder (for producing pressure) (not shown in the fig.).

FIG. 2
THIOUREA

Curves 1-5 refer respectively to 0.0104 M, 0.038 M, 0.086 M, 0.140 M and 0.184 M solns. in 1N-H₂SO₄. Solid line curve refers to 1N-H₂SO₄.

FIG. 3

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to 0.00106 M, 0.00796 M, 0.107 M and 0.030 M solns. in 1N-H₂SO₄. Topmost curve refers to 1N-H₂SO₄.

FIG. 4
DIETHYL AMINE

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to 0.816 M, 0.309 M, 0.424 M and 0.548 M solns. in 1N-H₂SO₄. Solid line curve refers to 1N-H₂SO₄.

FIG. 5

Curves 1-4 refer respectively to 0.0101 M, 0.0385 M and 0.126 M, 0.295 M solns. in 1N-H₂SO₄. Topmost curve refers to 1N-H₂SO₄.

The electrocapillary curves are shown in Figs. 2 to 7. They covered usually a wide range of inhibitor's concentration. It can be seen from these curves that tri-urea functions as a surface-active anion, while diethylamine, aniline, quinoline, β -naphthoquinoline and pyridine act mainly as surface-active cations. In the cases of quinoline and β -naphthoquinoline, the electrocapillary curves at φ -potential more negative than $-0.35 \div -0.45$ are distorted, apparently due to their reduction.

FIG. 6

Curves 1-6 refer respectively to 0.0000583 M, 0.000226 M, 0.000723 M, 0.00206 M, 0.00347 M and 0.00589 M solns. in 1N-H₂SO₄. Top curve refers to 1N-H₂SO₄.

FIG. 7

Curves 1-6 refer respectively to 0.0293 M, 0.0607 M, 0.101 M, 0.280 M, 0.419 M and 0.558 M solns. in 1N-H₂SO₄. Top most curve refers to 1N-H₂SO₄.

FIG. 8

Comparison with Corrosion Data

Principle of Comparison.—Addition of increasing amounts of an inhibitor to corrosion medium results in (a) decrease of corrosion rate, and (b) change of corrosion potential. The change of corrosion potential cannot be taken as a measure of inhibitor's efficiency, since the same reduction of corrosion current can be obtained at different values of corrosion potential (vide Fig. 8). It depends first of all on

the effect, which an inhibitor exerts on the polarisation of cathodic and anodic processes. The change of corrosion potential due to addition of organic compounds is normally small, and < 0.1 volt. Therefore, for all calculations made in this paper, the corrosion potential of iron in H_2SO_4 in presence of organic compounds is taken as a constant value of -0.28 volt against standard hydrogen electrode, in accordance with literature data.

The null-point of iron is equal to -0.02 volt, and therefore the corrosion potential given in φ -scale will be

$$E_{\varphi_{Cor}} = -0.28 - (-0.02) = -0.26 \text{ volt.}$$

FIG. 9

The most accurate value of null-point of mercury seems to be -0.19 volt, but in most cases, including the given case, the maximum point in electrocapillary curve

in 1N-H₂SO₄ corresponds to a potential of -0.21 volt, which therefore has been chosen as the null-point of mercury. A similar behaviour of the same organic compound in both corrosion and electrocapillary experiments can be obtained only at the same value of φ -potential. In the present case, the φ -potential equal to $\pi_{\varphi}^{\text{e.c.c.}} = -0.26$ (where e. c. c. = electrocapillary curve) is indicated in Fig. 2-7 by dotted line.

Results of Comparison.—The data obtained by Ride (*J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1956, 103, 98) have been used for comparison. These data correspond to corrosion of iron in 1N-H₂SO₄ at 25°. For thiourea, the data were taken from Hoar and Holliday's paper (*J. Appl. Chem.*, 1953, 3, 502). These data were obtained at 70°, but usually the values of inhibition coefficient, i.e. $K_i = i_0/i_1$ (i_0 and i_1 are rates of corrosion in absence and in presence of inhibitors respectively) vary with temperature not to a great extent, and a comparison is therefore possible.

The plot of $\log K_i$ against $\log C$, where C is the concentration of inhibitor, results in a series of straight lines (see Figs. 9 to 11) with different values of the slope.‡

The empirical relation,

$$\log K_i = \text{const}_1 + \beta_1 \log C \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

is true with the values of constants shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Thiourea	...	...	$\log K_i = 3.31 + 0.72 \log C$
β -Naphthoquinoline	...	..	$= 1.52 + 0.31 \text{ ,,}$
Diethylamine	...	..	$= 0.83 + 0.36 \text{ ,,}$
Quinoline	...	..	$= 0.83 + 0.29 \text{ ,,}$
Aniline	...	..	$= 0.70 + 0.61 \text{ ,,}$
Pyridine	...	..	$= 0.55 + 0.33 \text{ ,,}$

The electrocapillary data are represented in the same figures. It is also seen that in this case an approximately linear relation exists between $\log \Delta\sigma$ and $\log C$. The slope of these straight lines varies with the nature of compound and the value of potential. For each compound it is possible to find a value of potential at which the slopes of $\log K_i$ — $\log C$ and $\log \Delta\sigma$ — $\log C$ curves are equal. These values of potentials are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Compounds.	Value of φ -potential at which	Constants of eq. (3) at $\epsilon = 0.71$ volt	
	$\frac{\log \sigma \Delta}{\log C} = \frac{\log K_i}{\log C}$	($\varphi = -0.26$ V).	
		Const ₂	β_2
Thiourea	- 0.23	1.63	0.74
β -Naphthoquinoline	- 0.25	2.34	0.29
Quinoline	- 0.26	1.76	0.29
Diethylamine	- 0.23	1.15	0.41
Aniline	- 0.29	1.46	0.64
Pyridine	- 0.27	1.34	0.37

‡The graphical representation is shown here only for thiourea, quinoline and pyridine; for other compounds only the results of calculations based on the similar graphs are given.

FIG. 10

FIG. 11

The average value of potential at which the coincidence of the slopes is observed is equal to -0.255 V. Within the limits of experimental errors, it corresponds to the corrosion potential (-0.26) given in ϕ -scale. Hence, for the relation between $\Delta\sigma$ and C existing at the same potential as the corrosion potential in ϕ -scale, the equation (3) can be written as

$$\log \Delta\sigma = \text{const}_2 + \beta_2 \log C \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where β_2 is approximately equal to β_1 of equation (2).

DISCUSSION

From empirical equations (2) and (3), assuming that $\beta_1 = \beta_2$, the following relations can be obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \log K_1 &= \text{const}_1 - \text{const}_2 + \log \Delta\sigma \\ \text{or} \quad \log K_1 &= \text{const}_3 + \log \Delta\sigma \quad \dots \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

This equation indicates that inhibition coefficient is a function of surface activity. This relation ought to be expected because the influence of organic inhibitors is usually a result of their adsorption on metal-solution interface. But here the inhibition coefficient and adsorption are estimated for one and the same compound, but for two different metals. The equation (4) can be true when $\beta_1 = \beta_2$, and it takes place only when these two metals (in this particular case, iron and mercury) have the same value of ϕ -potential (here $\phi_{\text{Cor}} = \phi_{\text{Hg}} = -0.26$ V).

It means that the adsorption isotherm is within some limits independent of the nature of metal, if the process of adsorption is considered at the same value of ϕ -potential. At the same time, if this condition is not fulfilled, the data obtained for one metal could not be used for any suggestions concerning the process of adsorption

on other metal. So, for example, if iron and mercury be taken at the same potential in hydrogen scale $\eta_{\text{Hg}}^{\text{e.e.c.}} = \eta_{\text{Fe}}^{\text{e.c.}} = -0.28 \text{ V}$, then the slope of $\log \Delta\sigma - \log C$ will be quite different from the slope of $\log K_I - \log C$.*

If the surface activity would be the only factor that determines the inhibition properties of organic compounds, then at the given ϕ , the inhibition coefficient ought to be similarly independent of the nature of organic particles. Fig. 12 shows that surface activity is certainly very important, but not the sole property which determines the inhibition action of organic compounds.

The empirical relation between $\Delta\sigma$ and C can be derived on the basis of the Gibbs adsorption equation :

$$d\sigma = - qd\epsilon - \sum RT\Gamma d\ln C \quad \dots (5)$$

where, σ , q , ϵ , Γ and C are respectively interface tension, charge, potential of mercury surface, excess surface and volume concentration of each compound.

In case of only one compound (organic inhibitor of corrosion), equation (5) is simplified to

$$d\sigma = - qd\epsilon - RT\Gamma d\ln C \quad \dots (6)$$

In order to obtain an agreement with experimental data, it is necessary to make the following assumptions :

- (1) The potential remains constant : $d\epsilon = 0$.
- (2) The excess concentration is equal to the surface concentration : $\Gamma = C'$.
- (3) The latter is a Freundlich's type function of volume concentration :

$C' = K_I C^\beta$ then, from (6) and above,

$$d\sigma = - RT K_I C^\beta d\ln C$$

or after integration,
$$\sigma = - \frac{RT}{\beta} K_I C^\beta + \text{const.}$$

with C equal to 0, $\sigma = \sigma_0$;

hence the integration constant must be equal to $+\sigma_0$. Then,

$$\sigma_0 - \sigma = \Delta\sigma = \frac{RT}{\beta} K_I C^\beta \quad \dots \quad \dots (7)$$

or,
$$\log \Delta\sigma = \log \frac{RT}{\beta} K_I + \beta \log C = \text{const.}_2 + \beta \log C. \quad \dots (8)$$

The empirical formula (2) can be derived by many ways. So, it can be assumed that the energy of activation of rate-determining stage of corrosion process is a linear function of $\ln C' \gamma$, γ being a factor connected with size and other specific properties of inhibitor particles. In presence of an inhibitor, the equation of corrosion rate

$$i_{\text{Cor}} = \text{const. } e^{-\frac{\alpha e_1 F}{RT}} \quad \dots \quad \dots (8)$$

will be transformed to

$$i_{\text{Cor}} = \text{const. } e^{-\frac{\alpha e_2 F + RT \ln C' \gamma}{RT}}$$

* This value of potential corresponds to $\eta_{\text{Hg}} \phi = -0.28 - (-0.21) = -0.07 \text{ V}$ and to $\eta_{\text{Fe}} \phi = -0.28 - (-0.02) = -0.26 \text{ V}$ and the main condition of comparison ($\eta_{\text{Fe}} \phi = \eta_{\text{Hg}} \phi$) is not fulfilled.

and the inhibition coefficient will be represented as :

$$F_0 K_I = \frac{i_{Cor}}{i'_{Cor}} = e^{\frac{\alpha(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon_1)F + RT \ln C \gamma}{RT}} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

In many cases it is possible to neglect the change of potential, and (9) reduces to $F_0 K_I = C \gamma$ (10)

If the Freundlich formula is valid for the system under investigation then,

$$F_0 K_I = F_r K_I C^\beta$$

or, $\log K_I = \log F_0 K_I \gamma + \beta \log C = \text{const.}_1 + \beta \log C$ (11)

From equations (7) and (11) it is seen that the const._2 is a function of K_I for mercury and β , while the const._1 is a function of K_I for iron (or any other metal under comparison) and γ . Both of these constants are, hence, functions of the nature of metal and organic compound.

Therefore, it is natural to expect that these two constants also ought to satisfy one another in a functional relation.

If the specific constant β will be excluded from const._2 by adding the corresponding values of $\log \beta$, then for two given metals and for similar compounds, this relation ought to be of a similar type. Fig. 12 represents the relation between const._1 and $(\text{const.}_2 + \log \beta)$.

FIG. 12

The experimental points for pyridine, quinoline and β -naphthoquinoline are lying on the same straight line with a value of slope very near to 1. The points for aniline and diethylamine are in the vicinity of this straight line, but the point corresponding to thiourea is remote from it. It is seen therefore that the inhibition action depends on (a) the surface activity of compound at the potential of

corrosion, (b) on the size of particles in a given homologous series and (c) on the nature and number of surface active groups.

Application of the Method

Though these investigations are very far from being completed, many different applications of the method can be foreseen*.

* The idea of this method was formulated first by L. I. Antropov in a paper delivered at a Corrosion Congress (Moscow, Dec., 1955). Further development of this idea has been given by A. T. Petrenko (Thesis, Novotcherkassk, 1956) and V. P. Grigoriev (Thesis, Novotcherkassk, 1958). Their results are in a good agreement with those described in the present paper. Various applications of electrocapillary measurements and of ϕ -scale to corrosion of metals were considered in 1954-55 (Antropov, *Trans. Novotcherkassk Polytech. Inst.*, 1954, 28/39, 5; *Proc. V Corrosion Cong.*, 1955, 79, Moscow).

1. The coincidence of slopes of $\log K_i - \log C$ and $\log \Delta\sigma - \log C$ straight lines is observed at the potential of mercury equal to corrosion potential in φ -scale, which allows to predict the change of inhibitor's action with concentration. Really, if one value of inhibition coefficient is known, the values of K_i at any other concentration can be calculated by means of equation (2), using the value of β taken from electrocapillary measurements.

2. It is possible to predict the variation of inhibitor's action when the conditions of corrosion are changed. This can be illustrated by two examples:

(a) If the corrosion of iron will occur not in a pure sulphuric acid solution, but in the same solution containing some oxidising agent (ferric ions, potassium dichromate etc.), the value of corrosion potential will be changed in the positive direction. Let the new value of corrosion potential be equal to + 0.3 V in φ -scale. Then the surface activity of organic compounds ought to be estimated not at -0.26 V, as it was made in case of pure acid solution, but at + 0.3 V. The consideration of electrocapillary curves shows that here most of the cationic-like organic compounds (such as aniline, pyridine, quinoiline etc.) will be removed from the surface of corroding metal, and therefore they cannot be effective as inhibitors of corrosion. This fact* was stated by Elze and Fisher (*J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1952, 99, 259), who offered, however, a different explanation. On the other hand, anion-like compounds (e.g. thiourea) ought to be more effective, because their surface concentration will be increased. The change of inhibition action of molecular compounds will depend on their polar properties.

(b) It is well known that many attempts to find an effective inhibitor for prevention of Zn or Al corrosion in alkaline solution have failed. The reason of these unsuccessful searches is connected most probably with the highly negative values of corrosion potentials both for Zn and Al. So, the corrosion potential of Al in φ -scale is not $< \varphi_{\text{Cor}} = -1.1\text{V}$.

$$[\Delta\varphi_{\text{Cor}} = \Delta\varphi_{\text{Cor}} - \Delta\varphi_{\text{q}=0} = -1.5 - (-0.4) = -1.1\text{V}]$$

When these values of φ -potential are reached, the surface concentration of anions and anionic-like organic compounds ought to be very near to zero. The surface-active cations are replaced in the electric double layer by the smaller cations of alkali. The surface-active compounds of molecular nature are also withdrawn from the metal-solution interface by water molecules.

3. This method can be used for investigation of inhibition activity of different functional groups. If, as it was stated in the case of pyridine compounds, a simple relation between constants of equations (2) and (3) be found for other types of organic substances, the method can offer the possibility of calculation of inhibition activity only from electrocapillary measurements.

4. This method allows to formulate the conditions under which the application of many other methods, used for investigation of inhibition action, may lead to the positive results.

* Another reason for cessation of inhibitor's action may be connected with the fact that the kinetic limitations have been changed for the diffusion ones.

The capacity of electric double layer can be a measure of the surface activity of organic compounds. These data can be obtained with higher degree of accuracy only in case of mercury electrode. Because the adsorbability and, consequently, the differential capacity are functions of potential; only those values of capacities can be taken into consideration which correspond to the potential of mercury electrode equal to the potential of corroding metal given in the ϕ -scale.

The results of direct estimation of adsorption of different organic compounds from non-aqueous solution on the surface of metal under investigation cannot be quantitatively compared with the inhibition activity of the same compounds. The values of potentials in these two series of experiments (estimation of amounts of adsorbed particles and estimation of the magnitude of inhibition) can be very different. The different nature of solvents in case of adsorption and corrosion measurements can also distort the real state of things.

The suppression of polarographic maxima can be a measure of inhibition activity only when the position of maxima corresponds to the potential of corrosion given in the ϕ -scale (cf. Gatos, *J. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1954, 101, 433).

In the special case of iron corrosion in 1N-H₂SO₄, the position of maximum ought to be near to -0.26 V in ϕ -scale. Neither oxygen, nor lead and nickel maxima correspond to this condition. The potential of nickel maximum ($E_{Ni}^{\max} = -1.30 + 0.28 + 0.21 = -0.81$) is more negative than the corrosion potential, and the surface activity of cations will be increased and that of anions will be diminished in comparison with the adsorption of the same compounds on the surface of corroding iron. Better agreement can be expected only in case of organic compounds of molecular type. The potential of oxygen and probably of lead maxima are more positive than the value of corrosion potential of iron given in ϕ -scale. Therefore the condition of adsorption ought to be inversed with respect to nickel maximum.

All these methods, including electrocapillary curves method, can furnish under appropriate conditions the magnitude of adsorption of organic compounds on the surface of corroding metal. The surface activity is very important but, as it has been indicated above, it is not the single property of organic compound which alone determines its inhibitory action. The nature of these still-unknown properties may be hoped to be found as a result of systematic, comprehensive and relative study of adsorption of different organic compounds and their inhibition efficiency.

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